

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES WITH TRANSVERSE SHEAR EFFECTS

C. HUANG A. B. CHEIKH SAAD BOUH & G. VERCHERY

Materials and Mechanical Engineering Department
Ecole des Mines de Saint-Etienne
158, cours Fauriel
42023 St-Etienne Cedex 2, FRANCE

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the progressive failure analysis of composite laminates. Triangular elements which include the transverse shear effects are used for the stress analysis. A new method for the calculation of the shear correction factors is presented. Several failure criteria are used to check the first ply failure and distinguish the laminate failure modes into fibre breakage or buckling, matrix cracking and delamination. After the failure is detected, the stiffness of the failed ply is modified according to the failure modes. The ultimate strength of the laminate is obtained by an iterative way. Several examples are given in the paper for stress analysis and progressive failure analysis of composite laminates.

Key words : Composite Materials, Laminated Composites, Failure Analysis, Failure Criterion, Post-Failure, Transverse Shear, Damage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite laminate is a special kind of structure, which when partially damaged, will continue to bear load. It is very important to understand the behaviour of the composite laminate containing acceptable levels of damage and to predict the damage evolution in order to obtain the final strength of the structure. In recent years, the failure in fibre-reinforced laminated composites has been one of the extensively studied subjects. This problem usually concerns the following aspects : the definition of the structural model ; the accurate stress analysis ; the selection of the failure criteria and the post-failure structural stiffness adjustment. The mechanisms of damage progression and accumulation in laminated composites are extremely complicated. They are a combination of matrix cracking, fibre matrix splitting, fibre breakage and delamination, etc. Because of the complexity of this problem, any analytical solution may be impracticable, and the finite element method is probably the most suitable tool. Accurate stress analysis is very important in this problem for the prediction of more failure modes. Three dimensional elements may be used, but the calculating cost may be very high. Because the interlaminar stresses play an important role in the failure of laminates, the finite elements used in the program should include the transverse shear effects.

Many published results are available concerning this problem. Ochoa & Engblom ¹ introduced a 40-d.o.f., 8-node, through-thickness quadrilateral element for the stress analysis in which the transverse shear and normal stresses are considered. Different failure criteria are selected for fibre and matrix failures in tension and compression and for delamination in three-dimensional state of

stress. Then the constitutive relations of the failed elements are simply adjusted by setting some parameters to zero. The nonlinearity due to partial failures within a laminate was taken into consideration by Hwang & Sun ² and the Newton-Raphson iteration method was used to solve the nonlinear finite element equations. Chang ³ and Tan ⁴ used two-dimensional models for this problem. Stresses and strains in laminates were analyzed by Chang ³ on the basis of classical lamination theory with the consideration of material nonlinearity. Then several failure conditions were proposed to predict three inplane failure modes : matrix cracking, fibre-matrix shearing and fibre breakage. The degradation of the material property after failure was defined by either reducing the transverse modulus and Poisson's ratio to zero, or adjusting the longitudinal modulus and the shear modulus according to the Weibull distribution. The thermal and hygroscopic effects were taken into consideration by Tan ⁴, and the effects of the finite element mesh, load increment, etc, were also studied. Many numerical examples are provided in these references and the results are compared with the experiments. Huang & Verchery ⁵ introduced a new structural static reanalysis method in the iterative process to reduce the time for reanalysis.

In this paper, a 3-node, 15-d.o.f. triangular element is used for stress analysis. Besides the inplane stresses, the transverse shear stresses are also considered. We also present a simple method for calculating the shear correction factors, which proves to be very good compared with other methods. Several numerical examples are presented in the paper with excellent correlations with other references.

2. STRESS ANALYSIS

Accurate stress analysis is very important in order to predict failure modes. In this paper, we use a triangular element called DST (Discrete Shear Triangle) element developed by Lardeur ⁶. This is a two-dimensional element which considers the transverse shear effects and can be used for the analysis of thin to thick plates. The element is shown in Fig. 1. It has three node points, each with 5 degrees of freedom : $u_i, v_i, w_i, \theta_{xi}, \theta_{yi}$. The formulation is based on a generalization of the discrete-Kirchhoff technique to include the transverse shear effects. It has a proper rank and is free of shear locking. It also coincides with the DKT (Discrete Kirchhoff Triangle) element if the transverse shear effects are not significant.

In the formation of the element stiffness matrix, the relation between the shear force and the shear strain has to be set up, where shear correction factors are used. We use a simple but efficient method proposed by Cheikh Saad ⁷ to calculate these factors. The generalized Hooke's law for stress and strain fields considered in this paper is (x, y axes are in the plane of the laminate, and z axis is perpendicular to the laminate) :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{Q}_{21} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{Q}_{61} & \bar{Q}_{62} & \bar{Q}_{66} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{11} & \bar{C}_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{21} & \bar{C}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The relationship between the shear force \mathbf{T} and the shear strain $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ can be expressed as follows :

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{d} \mathbf{\Gamma} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{T} = (T_{xz}, T_{yz})^T$, $\mathbf{\Gamma} = (\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz})^T$, and \mathbf{d} is the generalized transverse stiffness matrix. The direct integration through the thickness of the laminate :

$$d_{ij}^* = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{C}_{ij} dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2) \quad (3)$$

usually gives too stiff results for the calculation of matrix \mathbf{d} and it is necessary to introduce correction factors to take into consideration the non-uniform distribution of the transverse shear over the laminate thickness. The following method, based on compliances, does not need such artificial factors.

A parabolic function is introduced to define the relationship between the shear stresses and the shear forces for composite laminates :

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{matrix} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} T_{xz} \\ T_{yz} \end{matrix} \right\} F(z) \quad (4)$$

where

$$F(z) = \frac{3}{2h} \left[1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (5)$$

Then the complement energy density due to the transverse shear is :

$$W_{ts} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{iz} \bar{S}_{ij} \tau_{jz} dz = \frac{1}{2} T_i \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{S}_{ij} F^2(z) dz T_j = \frac{1}{2} T^T H T \quad (6)$$

where

$$H_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{S}_{ij} F^2(z) dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2) \quad (7)$$

and \bar{S}_{ij} are the compliance parameters. Comparing Equation 3 and Equation 7, we have :

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{H}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

In order to compare with the classical approach, the correction factors k_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2$) can be introduced as :

$$\mathbf{d} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{11}d_{11}^* & k_{12}d_{12}^* \\ k_{21}d_{21}^* & k_{22}d_{22}^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

After the node displacements and the inplane stresses σ_x , σ_y , τ_{xy} are obtained, we can have the transverse shear stresses as :

$$\tau_{xz} = - \int_{-h/2}^z (\sigma_x' + \tau_{xy}' y) dz + C_x \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{yz} = - \int_{-h/2}^z (\tau_{xy}'_x + \sigma_{y'}_y) dz + C_y \quad (11)$$

where C_x, C_y are correction coefficients used to reduced the transverse shear stresses to zero at the upper and lower surface layers.

With this triangular element and the method presented above, we have calculated the stresses and displacements of a composite laminate, and compared the results with other numerical and analytical ones. Exact analytical solutions are available for this problem from Pagano & Hatfield ⁸, where a double sinusoidal distributed load is applied on the laminate surface :

$$q_0 = \sigma \sin(\pi x/L) \sin(\pi y/L) \quad (12)$$

In this paper, we first calculate the total force in each element by integrating this distributing force in each element with Gaussian integration, then distribute equally this force at each node of this element. The material properties are as follows : $E_{11}=25.0, E_{22}=1.0, G_{12}=0.5, G_{13}=0.5, G_{23}=0.2, \nu_{12}=0.25$. The final results are normalized in the following way :

$$(\bar{\sigma}_x, \bar{\sigma}_y, \bar{\tau}_{xy}) = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}) / \sigma S^2 \quad (13)$$

$$(\bar{\tau}_{xz}, \bar{\tau}_{yz}) = (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}) / \sigma S \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{w} = \pi^4 Q w / 12 S^4 h \sigma \quad (15)$$

$$Q = 4G_{12} + [E_{11} + E_{22}(1+2\nu_{23})] / (1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \quad (16)$$

where $S=L/h$, h is the thickness of the laminate, $L=1000$ is used in this example, w is the deflection at the central point of the laminate. The geometry of the laminate is shown in Fig. 2. Because of the symmetry, only one fourth of the structure is used in the finite element model. For boundary conditions, along AB : $w=\theta_y=0$; along BC : $u=\theta_x=0$; along CD : $v=\theta_x=0$; along DA : $w=\theta_x=0$. Two finite element meshes are used : one is 6×6 , another 10×10 . The laminate has three layers : $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$. The total thickness of the 0° and 90° layers are the same, whereas layers at the same orientation have equal thicknesses. Different ratios of length to thickness are considered. In Table 1 are listed the analysis results.

From Table 1, we can see that the deflection results have very good correlations with the exact analytical results. As for stresses, for very thick plate ($S=4$), there are some differences for σ_x and σ_{yz} . But as S increases, the results become much more satisfactory for all the stress components compared with the exact solutions.

Fig. 1 : The DST Element.

Fig. 2 : Geometry of the laminate for stress analysis.

Table 1 : Stresses and Displacements of the Laminate.

L/h		$\bar{\sigma}_x$ (L/2, L/2, h/2)	$\bar{\sigma}_y$ (L/2, L/2, h/4)	$\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ (0, L/2, 0)	$\bar{\sigma}_{yz}$ (L/2, 0, 0)	\bar{w} (L/2, L/2, 0)	
4	DST 6x6	0.3474	0.6956	0.1918	0.4008	4.5145	
	DST 10x10	0.3340	0.7394	0.1904	0.4025	4.5913	
	Ref.6	DST 6x6	0.4490	0.3720	0.1970	0.4150	4.4730
		DST 10x10	0.5180	0.2960	0.2020	0.4220	4.4900
	Ref. 8	0.7200	0.6660	0.2700	0.2920	4.4910	
10	DST 6x6	0.3806	0.5976	0.2892	0.1687	1.9236	
	DST 10x10	0.3535	0.6609	0.2820	0.1722	1.9570	
	Ref.6	DST 6x6	0.4780	0.3390	0.2030	0.4060	1.6980
		DST 10x10	0.5490	0.2530	0.2130	0.4090	1.7270
	Ref. 8	0.5590	0.4030	0.3010	0.1960	1.7090	
50	DST 6x6	0.5452	0.3098	0.3054	0.1472	1.0769	
	DST 10x10	0.4772	0.3431	0.3238	0.1344	1.1046	
	Ref.6	DST 6x6	0.4940	0.3460	0.1590	0.3530	1.0670
		DST 10x10	0.4940	0.3310	0.1600	0.4360	1.0250
	Ref. 8	0.5390	0.2760	0.3370	0.1410	1.0310	
10 ⁴	DST 6x6	0.5313	0.2750	0.3989	0.1590	0.9895	
	DST 10x10	0.5355	0.2716	0.4152	0.1585	0.9963	
	Ref. 8	0.5390	0.2690	0.3390	0.1380	1.0000	

3. FAILURE CRITERIA

The laminate failure modes can be classified as fibre failure, matrix failure, delamination, etc. Fibre failure mode is described by fibre breakage under tension or fibre buckling under compression. Matrix failure mode is described by plane failure surface parallel to fibres or compressive matrix failure mode. Delamination mode is produced by the interlaminar stresses.

After the stresses in each lamina in each elements are obtained, the following failure criteria are used to check the ply failure (let 1 denote the fibre direction, 2 be perpendicular to the fibre direction, and 3 be perpendicular to the plate) :

For fibre failure :

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 > 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_c}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 < 0 \quad (18)$$

For matrix cracking :

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_2 > 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_2}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_2 < 0 \quad (20)$$

The delamination occurs if :

$$\sqrt{\tau_{13}^2 + \tau_{23}^2} \geq S_1 \quad (21)$$

with the following definitions :

X_T	longitudinal tensile strength,	X_C	longitudinal compressive strength,
Y_T	transverse tensile strength,	Y_C	transverse compressive strength,
S_{12}	shear strength in the 1-2 plane,	S_{13}	shear strength in the 1-3 plane,
S_{23}	shear strength in the 2-3 plane,	S_1	interlaminar shear strength.

These failure criteria are applied to each lamina of the laminate in all the elements. The stresses in the centre of the triangular element are used for failure check. The ply may fail in one mode only, or in several combined modes mentioned above.

4. STIFFNESS DEGRADATION

After the ply has failed, the stiffness of the ply is changed according to the ply failure modes. In this paper, we use a simple post-failure stiffness adjustment method. For example, if fibre failure has occurred, we will change the constitutive relation of the failed ply as :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Q_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

If matrix cracking or delamination has occurred, then the following relation is introduced :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

If both fibre and matrix failures have occurred, then the whole ply will be removed from the laminate. In actual calculation, the complete disappearance of the parameters C_{11} , C_{22} will cause some problem, for the inverse of them are used in the program. So instead of zero values, they are assigned very small non-zero values.

When some plies have failed, the stress will redistribute in the plate. After the constitutive relations of the failed ply are modified, the element stiffness matrix will be calculated again, then another stress analysis is performed to obtain the new stress distribution in the laminate.

5. PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS

The progressive failure analysis of composite laminates involves a step-by-step procedure. For a given load, the stresses in each lamina of each element are calculated, then failure check is performed according to the criteria mentioned above. After the stiffness of the failed ply is modified, the stresses are recalculated at the same load level. This process is continued until no failure is found in the laminate. Then the load is increased to start another analysis. The process is terminated if substantial failures have occurred in the laminate, when the ultimate strength of the laminate is reached.

The algorithm mentioned above is applied to a composite laminate for progressive failure analysis. This is a rectangular plate with a central open hole. The geometry of the laminate is shown in Fig. 3. Two ends of the plate are completely fixed. A constant distributing force perpendicular to the plate is exerted on the plate surface.

The lay-up of the laminate is $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3/0^\circ]_S$. The material properties are : $E_{11}=138$ GPa, $E_{22}=10.3$ GPa, $G_{12}=6.6$ GPa, $G_{23}=2.6$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.21$. lamina thickness $\tau_0 = 1.32 \times 10^{-4}$ m, $X_T = 1.393$ GPa, $X_C = 1.4479$ GPa, $Y_T = 44.8$ MPa, $Y_C = 172.4$ MPa, $S_{12} = S_{13} = S_{23} = 62.1$ MPa, $S_I = 34.5$ MPa. The finite element model is shown in Fig. 4. Only one fourth of the structure is considered because of the symmetry. In this model, there are 152 nodes, 252 triangular elements. The stresses at the center of the triangular element in the middle of the thickness of each lamina are used to present the stress level of each lamina in this element. For boundary conditions, along AB : $u = \theta_y = 0$; along BC : $u = v = w = \theta_x = \theta_y = 0$; along DE : $v = \theta_x = 0$.

The initial distributing load on the surface of the laminate is 0.25 MPa. The increment of the load is 0.05 MPa. At the initial load, matrix crackings have been found in some elements on the boundary of the hole and at the end of the plate for the upper and lower outmost 0° layers, as shown in Fig. 5. The number within the elements refers to the lamina where matrix cracks have occurred.

When the load is increased to 0.3 MPa, delaminations have occurred in the elements on the boundary of the hole and at the end of the laminate in the central layers, as shown in Fig. 2.11. In the figure, the number without an underline indicates the lamina in which matrix has cracked, the number underlined refers to the lamina where delamination has occurred.

At 0.45 MPa, fibres in the 90° have broken in the elements on the boundary of the hole. Many matrix cracks have appeared near the hole region and at the end of the plate, mostly in the two zero degree laminae. More delaminations are observed near the hole region and at the end of the plate, mostly happened around the middle of the laminate thickness. Because of the larger number of layers and elements damaged, it is quite difficult to represent them in figures.

The ultimate strength is reached at the load of 0.7 MPa, when substantial matrix crackings and delaminations are found in most of the elements. No fibre buckling is observed. This ultimate strength may be a little bit conservative, because of the method used for stiffness modification of the failed laminae.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a triangular element considering transverse shear effects is used to study the progressive failure analysis of laminated composites. The method for the calculation of the shear correction factors is very efficient, as shown by the comparison of the displacements and stresses with exact analytical solutions. More failure modes are introduced than by using elements without shear effects. It is observed that these extra modes are active in some steps of the failure process. The criteria introduced are able to predict in detail various failure modes, however the method for the modification of the ply post-failure behaviour should be improved by introducing more refined models. This would improve greatly the analysis to take complete advantage of composite material properties.

Fig. 3 : Geometry of the laminate with an open hole.

Fig. 4 : Finite element mesh.

Fig. 5 : Matrix cracks in certain laminae of some elements at initial load.

Fig. 6 : Damage propagation at the second load level.

7. REFERENCES

1. Ochoa O. O. and Engblom J. J., "Analysis of Progressive Failure in Composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 28, pp. 87-102, 1987.
2. Hwang W. C., Sun C. T., "Failure Analysis of Laminated Composites by Using Iterative Three-Dimensional Finite Element Method ;" *Computer & Structures*, Vol. 33, No. 1, pp. 41-47, 1989
3. Chang F.K. and Chang K.Y., "A Progressive Damage Model for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations," *J. of Composite materials*, Vol. 21, pp. 834-855, 1987.
4. Tan S. C., "A Progressive Failure Model for Laminated Composites Containing an Opening", Proceedings of ICCM/VIII, 31-J, 1991.
5. Huang C. and Verchery G., "Analysis of Progressive Failure for Laminated Composites", Proceedings of the Second International Symposium on Textile Composites in Building Construction, Part 2, pp. 87-100, June 23-25, 1992, Lyon, France.
6. Lardeur P., "Développement et Evaluation de Deux Nouveaux Eléments Finis de Plaques et Coques Composites avec Influence du Cisaillement Transversal" ; Doctoral dissertation, Université de Technologie de Compiègne, 1990.
7. Cheikh Saad Bouh, "Evaluation des Performances de Divers Eléments Finis et des Effets d'Anisotropie pour les Plaques Composites en Flexion," Doctoral dissertation, Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, 1992.
8. Pagano N.J. and Hatfield S.J., "Elastic Behaviour of Multilayered Bidirectional Composites", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 10, No. 7, pp. 931-933, 1972.